

Addressing COVID-19 Testing Inequities Among Underserved Populations in Massachusetts (MA)

- Community health centers (CHC) have played a critical role in addressing the COVID-19 testing needs of historically disadvantaged communities.
- We explored the views of COVID-19 testing barriers in six MA communities that are predominately low-income.
- Our findings were used to build community-specific strategies to address testing inequities.

Scan QR code to read the full article!

WHO PARTICIPATED

107 CHC staff, community partners and residents

We did **qualitative interviews over Zoom and phone**. Resident interviews were conducted in English, Vietnamese, Arabic and Spanish.

WHAT WE DID

WHAT WE FOUND

Barriers to testing included: **access to state-run testing sites, weak social safety nets, and lack of testing suppliers and staffing that made wait time longer.**

This increased fears around testing and limited knowledge on testing availability.

Partnering CHCs were able to use these data to help the local needs of each community.

This study shows the structural disparities of people's experience of COVID-19 and how we can translate data for action in real time (especially for a rapidly evolving pandemic).